

UNITED4Surveillance pilot report (Latvia)

1. Describe the aim and objectives of your pilot study

The aim of the Latvian pilot was to strengthen the surveillance of severe infections that lead to hospitalisation by introducing a digital urgent notification form for timely and structured reporting of such cases by healthcare professionals; electronic notification form popularization and further development. The objectives included implementing the form in medical institutions, promoting its routine use, preparing for data linkage with laboratory results, vaccination records, and mortality data, and initiating changes in national legislation to support digital notification workflows.

These objectives were partially achieved during the pilot. The electronic urgent notification form was successfully introduced and actively used by a wide range of medical professionals. Initial work toward data integration was carried out through collaboration with laboratories and system providers. Proposals for legislative amendments were prepared to support future implementation and sustainability of the system. These results represent significant progress toward the original objectives, despite limitations related to funding and technical infrastructure.

2. Describe the expected output prior to start of the pilot

Previously, we did not have an electronic urgent notification form. It was not digitalized. A solution was developed, and we would like to promote it. We regularly monitor the situation and collect statistical data.

The expected outputs of the Latvian pilot included: the development and piloting of an electronic urgent notification form for SARI cases in selected hospitals; the preparation for data linkage with laboratory test results, vaccination records, and mortality data; and the initiation of legal amendments to support the implementation of a digital surveillance system.

These outputs were partially achieved during the pilot. The electronic urgent notification form was successfully developed, introduced, and actively used by a wide range of medical professionals. Initial work toward data integration was carried out through collaboration with laboratories and system providers. Proposals for legislative amendments were prepared to support future implementation and sustainability of the system. These results reflect meaningful progress toward the original goals, despite limitations related to funding and system-wide technical capacity.

3. Briefly describe the method(s) used

The pilot combined technical implementation with stakeholder engagement and real-world testing. The digital urgent notification form was introduced in hospitals, general practitioner practices, and outpatient institutions. Healthcare professionals were supported through training materials, information sessions, individual consultations, and regular technical assistance. During the initial phase of our pilot, we also visited several hospitals in person to demonstrate how to use the form.

Statistical data on the use of the system was collected throughout the pilot, and feedback from users was gathered to identify needs for improvement. Discussions were held with IT system providers and laboratories to prepare for future data integration. Legal experts and public health professionals collaborated to draft proposals for amendments to the regulatory framework supporting electronic reporting.

4. Report the principal finding(s) of your pilot study

The pilot demonstrated that the introduction of a digital urgent notification form is feasible, acceptable, and effective in supporting surveillance of severe infections requiring hospitalisation. More than 3,000 electronic urgent notifications were submitted by 782 healthcare professionals, including general practitioners, outpatient specialists, and nearly all state-funded hospitals.

The number of notifications steadily increased throughout the pilot, indicating growing adoption and awareness. Regular support and training contributed to user confidence and consistent system use. Feedback collected from healthcare providers highlighted both the benefits of the system and areas for future improvement.

The experience confirmed that digital notification improves timeliness, data completeness, and reduces administrative burden compared to paper-based reporting. It also supports the transition toward integrated surveillance by enabling future linkage with laboratory and vaccination data.

5. Formulate your main take-away(s) and recommendations of your pilot study and provide rationale(s)

The main takeaway of the pilot is that a digital urgent notification system is both practical and effective for improving infectious disease surveillance in hospital settings. When supported by clear guidance, training, and communication, healthcare professionals adopt the system readily and use it consistently.

Key recommendations based on the pilot experience:

- Continue promoting the use of the digital notification form by expanding training and support activities;
- Finalize and adopt the proposed legal amendments to formally enable electronic reporting and reduce reliance on paper-based systems;
- Secure funding to improve the existing system, particularly to enhance usability and ensure integration with laboratory, vaccination, and mortality databases;
- Develop a national transition plan to gradually phase out paper-based notification and scale up digital solutions across all relevant healthcare settings.

These steps will help ensure sustainability, increase data quality and timeliness, and reduce administrative burden for healthcare providers. This digital solution can contribute to reducing underreporting and is an integral part of the broader digitalization process in the healthcare sector.

6. Reflect on most relevant limitations and/or challenges (including potential solutions) and the degree of achieving expected output of your pilot study

We are working with a wide range of stakeholders, including healthcare professionals from various specialties, hospitals, and laboratories. The most relevant challenges were related to limited national funding, which restricted the scope of IT development, and the high cost of external technical services, which made it difficult to implement certain planned components.

In addition, although efforts were made to apply for external funding, the absence of a formal mandate from the Ministry of Health limited the ability to access international grant opportunities.

Delays in the development of a centralized IT system for laboratories — which was expected to support data integration — also limited progress in linking case notifications with laboratory results. Moreover, there was no dedicated funding to support migration from the legacy system to a modernized platform.

Despite these limitations, the pilot achieved its core objectives:

- The digital notification form was developed, implemented, and widely adopted;
- Healthcare professionals were trained and supported;
- Legal proposals were prepared;
- The foundation for future system integration was established.

These achievements demonstrate that meaningful progress can be made even under constrained conditions, provided there is strong engagement with end users and stakeholders.

7. Did your pilot study contribute to strengthened (inter)national infectious disease surveillance? Why or why not?

Yes, the pilot contributed significantly to strengthening both national and international infectious disease surveillance. By introducing a digital urgent notification system for severe infections requiring hospitalisation, the pilot improved the timeliness, completeness, and accessibility of surveillance data. The system enabled more efficient communication between healthcare providers and public health authorities, and supported improved coordination between national systems — particularly the e-health platform and the EPID database. The digital format also reduces administrative burden and the risk of underreporting, helping align national practice with broader EU goals for integrated, interoperable digital public health infrastructure.

The pilot is ongoing, and the promotion of the electronic urgent notification form continues through updated training materials, online seminars, and individual consultations. The solution is well-received by medical professionals, but several limitations and areas for improvement have been identified — including technical refinements and better integration with other digital systems. Continued training and system development will be essential for broader adoption and long-term success. The notification system can serve as a key component in the wider digitalisation of the healthcare sector. The pilot created a strong foundation for further system development, expansion, and eventual international data sharing.

UNITED4 Surveillance legal/privacy barriers (template)

1. To what degree did you experience legal/privacy barrier(s) in your pilot study?

No	Little	Some	Large	Very large
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2. If so, please provide a detailed example(s) on the experienced legal/privacy barrier(s) in your pilot study.

Minor legal/privacy challenges were related to the lack of specific regulatory provisions formally enabling the routine use of electronic urgent notification forms. This occasionally caused uncertainty among healthcare providers regarding data handling responsibilities and system use in parallel with existing paper-based procedures. Protecting personal data is more challenging with paper-based forms. In contrast, the electronic notification form significantly reduces these barriers, offering a more secure and efficient solution.

3. How did you cope with and/or solve the experienced legal and/or privacy barrier within your pilot study? If not, what is your suggestion to solve this legal/privacy barrier(s) in the future?

To address these concerns, we provided clear communication to healthcare institutions about the legal basis and data protection safeguards of the digital system.

We also prepared and submitted proposals for amendments to the relevant national regulations, aiming to formally support and clarify the use of electronic urgent notifications. In parallel, we emphasized that digital reporting improves data security compared to paper forms transmitted via email, and helps reduce privacy risks in the long term.